

TOPOGRAPHIC MAPS ON THE TRACKS

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Abstract: *All topographical and visual topographical maps are made in the equiangular cross-cylindrical projection of the German scientists Gauss and Krueger. The area depicted on topographic maps is divided into parts of a certain size, and each of them is depicted on a separate sheet.*

Key words: *Topographic, scale, scale, general geographic, geodetic.*

Topographic maps are detailed general geographic maps that describe the main natural and socio-economic objects and have a single content, decoration and mathematical basis. It is created using a system of stable conditional girders on a rigid geodesic basis. They include the appearance of the geographical landscape and its main elements - relief, hydrography, vegetation, soil cover, settlements, roads, and industry, agriculture. and other social infrastructure objects are depicted with the same accuracy and perfection (see the color map on page 499). Topographic maps are made at scales of 1:10,000, 1:25,000, 1:50,000 and 1:100,000. Each topographic map is named after its scale. For example, if the scale is 1:10,000, it is called Topographic maps, if it is ten thousand, if it is 1:25,000 - twenty-five thousand. The scale of topographic maps is given in the table below. The elements of topographic maps can be summarized and divided into 2 groups - mathematical and geographical elements. Mathematical elements include map grid, scale, frame, sheeting and nomenclature, and geodetic datums. Geographic elements include details of the earth's surface that are depicted on topographic maps. Elements of topographic maps are closely related to each other, and they are described using special fixed conventional symbols and

notations. Topographic maps are widely used in the complete study and inspection of a place, in the design and construction of various structures, in the performance of engineering works such as accurate measurement and calculation, in orientation in a place, and for military purposes. All topographical and visual topographical maps are made in the equiangular cross-cylindrical projection of the German scientists Gauss and Krueger. The area depicted on topographic maps is divided into parts of a certain size, and each of them is depicted on a separate sheet. Each sheet of topographic or obser Topographic maps is bounded by meridian and parallel lines and has the shape of a trapezoid. Dividing a multi-sheet map into separate sheets into graphs and marking them according to a certain system is called nomenclature. The nomenclature of all Topographic maps is based on the division and nomenclature of the international map at a scale of 1:1,000,000. The international nomenclature system was adopted at the international geographical congresses held in London in 1909 and Paris in 1913. According to this system, the width of a 1:1,000,000 scale map sheet is 4° in the meridian and 6° in the parallel.

Parallels are drawn every 4° from the equator to the poles, and columns are formed from the meridian every 6° starting from the 180° meridian. The rows are marked with the capital letters of the Latin alphabet (A to Z) from the equator to both sides, and the columns are marked with Arabic numerals 1 to 60, starting from the 180° meridian, in the order of increasing counterclockwise. Thus, the nomenclature of each sheet of a 1:1,000,000 scale map consists of a letter designating a row and a number indicating a column number. Mac, Tashkent sh. the nomenclature of the sheet on which it is located is K-42, and that of the city of Moscow is designated as N-37. The table below shows the size and nomenclature of one sheet (trapezium) of topographic maps. Topographic maps are created and published on the basis of the same standard scales, conventional signs and guidelines in all organizations. The details depicted on the topographic maps are colored to match the natural color of the surface, so that they can be distinguished from each other and quickly understood. For example, the contours of forests, gardens, vineyards, bushes and other vegetation

- in green, contours or conventional signs of water, i.e. sea, ash, river, canal, reservoir, pond, spring, etc. - in air color, relief and its elements, i.e. bay, ravine, sand and others are depicted in brown. Inscriptions used on topographic maps not only make it easier to distinguish color details and map the map, but also enrich the content of the map and act as a conditional symbol to a certain extent. A dome-shaped or conical height rising from the surrounding plain is called a hill. The relative density of the top is up to 200 mg. A hill with a relative height of up to 100 m is called a dune. A continuous series of hills is called a ridge. Its relative height is up to 200 mg. It is the height expected above the surrounding plain. The mountain can be dome-shaped, cone-shaped, pyramid-shaped and other shapes, the height of the mountain exceeds 500 m. The highest part of the mountain is called the peak, and the peaks with sharp points are called chukki. The mountains that continue to Katorasi form a mountain range. The junction of two or more mountain ranges is called a mountain node (node). The largest of the batik landforms is the valley. The length, width, and depth of the valleys are different. Hill, mountain slopes are different: smooth convex concave terraced and can be complex. The slope of the smooth side does not change. The slope of the side is measured by the slope angle.

References

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